

Commensurability demonstrator made with LEGO™ pieces

Additional materials:

- washers or small weights;
- weak/small spring or a Newton-meter;
- and thread or string.

Optional materials are blu-tac or double-sided tape for fixing the demonstrator in place on a table, should you wish.

Use

During the final assembly step, you may wish to add washers or small weights using the six pins on top of the tip. Before or after mounting the slider in place on top of the surface, tie some string around the middle of the slider bar, ensuring to go through the two holes wither side of the slider arm. At the end of the string attach the spring and another small amount of string (or a loop to attach a Newton-meter). Like this:

Pulling the slider across the surface and examining the length of the spring will give a good indicator of changes in friction.

Adding more weights will increase the friction of the system. See the “Features” section to see what else can affect the friction of the system.

Features

The frame and surface are free to slide against each other, and the surface can be positioned differently relative to the tip. There is enough space within the frame to for a wide range of movement. The surface is fixed into place relative to the slider using moveable parts at either end of the frame. Using this you can achieve different levels of commensurability between the tip and the surface.

The tip can be rotated and locked using the stoppers. The blue cog has 12 teeth and the stoppers with the grey tip, lock the teeth parallel with the slider bar. This can be used to give a leading flat edge or a leading point on the slider.

The slider's arm is not vertically fixed in position, allowing the tip to rise up and down in contact with the surface. This should also allow for a constant normal force.

Tweaks

If you wish to tweak the model, simply download and install BrickLink.com's free design program [Studio](#). Then you can use this program to open the design file for this model:

“CommensurabilityDemonstrator.io”.

Parts list

To order this model please see “OrderingLEGO.pdf”.

List as .csv file: “Commensurability.csv”.

Image	Description	Item No (& alternate Item Nos)	Colour	Qty
	Brick 1 x 1	3005 30071 35382	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	12
	Technic, Brick 1 x 1 with Axle Hole	73230	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Technic, Brick 1 x 1 with Hole	6541	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	6
	Brick 1 x 2	3004 93792	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Technic, Brick 1 x 2 with Axle Hole	31493 32064	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Vertical End	51478 30364	Black	2
	Slope 45 1 x 2	3040 6270 35281	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Slope, Inverted 45 1 x 2	3665	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Brick 1 x 3	3622 45505	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	10
	Brick 1 x 4	3010 6146	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Technic, Brick 1 x 4 with Holes	3701	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Brick 1 x 6	3009 30611	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Brick 1 x 8	3008 63322	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	6
	Brick 1 x 10	6111	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4

	Brick, Modified Facet 2 x 2	87620			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	12
	Brick 2 x 3	3002			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Slope 45 2 x 4	3037			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Brick, Round 2 x 2 with Pin Holes	17485	79566		Bright Blue or Blue	8
	Plate 1 x 1	3024 63326	28554	30008	Bright Blue or Blue	2
	Plate 1 x 1	3024 63326	28554	30008	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	48
	Plate 1 x 2	3023	6225	28653	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Hinge Plate 1 x 2 Locking with 1 Finger on End without Bottom Groove	49715	44301		Black	2
	Hinge Plate 1 x 2 Locking with 2 Fingers	54657	44302		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Plate, Modified 1 x 2 with 1 Stud with Groove and Bottom Stud Holder (Jumper)	15573	78823		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate, Modified 1 x 2 with Bar Arm Up (Horizontal Arm 5mm)	43876	88072	4623	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate 1 x 3	3623			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	10
	Plate, Modified 1 x 3 with 2 Studs (Double Jumper)	34103			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Plate 1 x 4	3710			Bright Blue or Blue	4
	Plate 1 x 4	3710			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	26
	Plate, Modified 1 x 4 with Bar Arm Down	29169	30043		Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	2

	Plate 1 x 5	78329	Earth Blue or Dark Blue	12
	Plate 1 x 5	78329	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	14
	Plate 1 x 6	3666	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	7
	Plate 1 x 8	3460	Bright Blue or Blue	2
	Plate 1 x 8	3460	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Plate 1 x 8	3460	Medium Azur or Medium Azure	32
	Plate 1 x 12	60479	Earth Blue or Dark Blue	20
	Plate 1 x 12	60479	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	10
	Wedge, Plate 2 x 2 Cut Corner	26601	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Plate 2 x 3	3021 03021	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Wedge, Plate 2 x 3 Left	43723	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Wedge, Plate 2 x 3 Right	43722	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate 2 x 6	3795	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate 2 x 14	91988	Earth Blue or Dark Blue	2
	Plate 2 x 16	4282	Bright Blue or Blue	5
	Plate 3 x 3 Corner	77844	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	4

	Plate, Modified 3 x 3 Cross	15397			Black	14
	Plate 4 x 4	3031			Black	2
	Plate 4 x 4	3031			Earth Blue or Dark Blue	2
	Plate 4 x 4	3031			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Plate 4 x 4	3031			Medium Azur or Medium Azure	2
	Wedge, Plate 4 x 4 Cut Corner	30503			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Plate 4 x 6	3032			Black	2
	Plate 4 x 8	3035			Black	4
	Plate 4 x 12	3029			Black	4
	Plate 6 x 10	3033			Black	8
	Plate 8 x 16	92438			Black	6
	Plate, Round 2 x 2 with Rounded Bottom (Boat Stud)	2654 93791	28558	54196	Bright Blue or Blue	133
	Plate, Round 2 x 2 with Rounded Bottom (Boat Stud)	2654 93791	28558	54196	Dark Azur or Dark Azure	3
	Plate, Round 2 x 2 with Rounded Bottom (Boat Stud)	2654 93791	28558	54196	Earth Blue or Dark Blue	3
	Plate, Round 2 x 2 with Rounded Bottom (Boat Stud)	2654 93791	28558	54196	Bright Orange or Orange	19
	Technic, Plate Rotor 3 Blade with Smooth Ends and 6 Studs (Propeller)	51138	32125		Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	2

	Tile 1 x 2	3069 37293 88630	30070 45880 113482	35386 54285	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	6
	Tile, Modified 1 x 3 Inverted with Hole	35459			Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	2
	Tile 1 x 6	6636 112417	63324	75702	Bright Blue or Blue	10
	Tile 1 x 6	6636 112417	63324	75702	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	10
	Tile 1 x 8	4162	40929		Bright Blue or Blue	10
	Tile 1 x 8	4162	40929		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	10
	Tile 2 x 2 Corner	14719			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Tile, Modified Facet 2 x 2	27263 54578	1134 112413	39726	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4
	Tile 2 x 4	87079	38879	71150	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Tile 2 x 6	69729			Earth Blue or Dark Blue	1
	Tile 2 x 6	69729			Medium Azur or Medium Azure	1
	Tile, Round 2 x 2 with Open Stud	18674			Earth Blue or Dark Blue	8
	Tile, Round 2 x 2 with Open Stud	18674			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	158
	Technic Bush	42798	3713	6590	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	4
	Technic, Liftarm Thin 1 x 6	28570	32063		Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	2
	Technic, Liftarm Thick 1 x 7	32524	16615		Bright Orange or Orange	2

	Technic, Liftarm Thick 1 x 11	64290	32525	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	1
	Technic, Liftarm, Modified Bent Thick 1 x 11.5 Double	41486	32009	Bright Orange or Orange	8
	Technic, Link Tread Attachment, Single, Rubber	24375		Black	4
	Technic, Pin 1/2 without Friction Ridges	4274	89678	Bright Blue or Blue	8
	Technic, Pin 3L with Friction Ridges	42924	6558	Bright Blue or Blue	8
	Bar 2L with Stop Ring	78258		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	6
	Technic, Arm with Gear 8 Tooth and 1.5L Axle	24014		Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	4
	Technic, Axle 3L	4519	32240	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	8
	Technic, Axle 8L with Stop	55013		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	1
	Technic, Axle 32L	13927	50450	Black	2
	Technic, Gear 12 Tooth	69778		Bright Blue or Blue	2
	Technic, Gear 24 Tooth with 1 Axle Hole	24505	3648	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	2
	Technic, Gear Rack 1 x 4	4296	3743	Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	4